

Kinetics and mechanism of electron-transfer reactions : Oxidation of dimethyl sulfoxide by chromium(VI) in acid perchlorate medium

Seema Sharma, Riya Sailani*, C. L. Khandelwal and P. D. Sharma

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : l.p_riya@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 22 February 2011, revised 05 July 2011, accepted 12 July 2011

Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) by chromium(VI) has been studied in acid perchlorate medium. The reaction is second order-first order with respect to each reactant. Hydrogen ion dependence is complex. The kinetic rate law is represented by eq. (1).

$$-\frac{2}{3} \frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = \{k_1[\text{H}^+]^2 + k_2[\text{H}^+]^3\}[\text{DMSO}][\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] \quad (1)$$

The probable mechanism corresponding to rate law (1) has been suggested. Activation parameters have also been evaluated.

Keywords : Kinetics, mechanism, oxidation, dimethyl sulfoxide, chromium(VI).

Introduction

Chromium(VI) has frequently and extensively been employed as an oxidizing agent both for preparative as well as analytical methods in chemistry. Chromic acid, aqueous dichromate, chromyl chloride, chromyl acetate and other substituted chromates have been employed in oxidation of organic as well as inorganic compounds in aqueous acid and alkaline media. It is the reason for which the analytical chemists in general and kineticists in particular are attracted to know more about such an interesting chemistry of this reagent¹⁻¹⁶. It is the reactivity of this reagent towards a large number of compounds that critical reviews have come out in the past¹⁷⁻²⁴.

It is worth mentioning that different view-points have been put forth to delineate the reactivity pattern of this oxidant²⁵⁻²⁷. The primary controversial observations are related to the reactivity of its intermediates, rate dependence on the hydrogen ion concentration and the nature of complex formation of the oxidant with the substrates.

There are also reports which are related to the dependence of rate on hydrogen ion concentration in oxidation of sulfoxides. However, such dependence has not been properly accounted for in the rate equation. These were

certain observations that initiated our interest to explore the title reaction to know more about the reaction events in further details. Since the system appears to be clean so far as the oxidation of the substrate is concerned, the problem to be looked into is purely related to the oxidant whether it is monomeric, dimeric or both. Secondly, whether or not the hydrogen ion dependence is related to the oxidant, substrate or both.

Further the transformation of the organic substrate is reported²⁸ as follows yielding various types of the products under varied environments of the reactions.

Since, the transformation of DMSO to various types of products depends upon the nature and potentiality of the oxidizing reagent; this is our additional interest to

undertake the title reaction to understand such reaction events more precisely.

Experimental

The experimental details regarding the preparation and standardization of chromium(VI) solution have already been mentioned elsewhere. However, all other chemicals employed in this study were either of AnalaR or reagent grade and were used as received.

Doubly distilled water was employed throughout the study. The second distillation was done using alkaline permanganate solution.

Reaction mixtures containing required concentrations of all other reaction components except chromium(VI) were taken in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks, the later were suspended in a water-bath thermostated at ± 0.1 °C unless stated otherwise. The reactions were initiated by adding temperature pre-equilibrated requisite volume of chromium(VI) solution. However, initiation of the reaction by dimethyl sulfoxide was without any effect.

The kinetics of the reaction was monitored by withdrawing an aliquot of the reaction mixture periodically and then discharging it into a freshly prepared KI solution ($\sim 10\%$) in H_2SO_4 ($\sim 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The liberated iodine was titrated against thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator. The kinetic measurements in triplicate were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$.

The preliminary kinetics indicate disappearance of chromium(VI) to be a first order process, the pseudo-first order rate constants decrease with increasing gross initial concentration of the oxidant pointing towards a monomeric-dimeric equilibrium of chromium(VI) species participating in the reaction under such experimental conditions.

Stoichiometry :

The reactions with sufficient excess concentration of chromium(VI) over that of dimethyl sulfoxide were allowed to occur in a thermostated water bath at 45 ± 0.1 °C for *ca.* 8 h and the excess of the oxidant was assayed iodometrically. The results indicate that two moles of chromium(VI) react with three moles of DMSO as represented by eq. (1).

Sulfone has also been reported to be the oxidation product of dimethyl sulfoxide in other chemical reactions²⁹⁻³⁴. Further IR spectral analysis of the aqueous solution also confirms formation of dimethyl sulfone to be the oxidation product of sulfoxide. Further, dimethyl sulfone is not oxidized by chromium(VI) under experimental conditions¹².

Product analysis :

The IR spectrum of the oxidation product of DMSO in aqueous solution was obtained by employing FTIR 85005 (Shimadzu) with KRS-5 cell of thickness 0.5 mm.

The IR spectrum of the product exhibits two absorption bands in the regions 1350–1400 and 1050 cm^{-1} respectively which may be attributed to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of SO_2 group. The absorption band at 520 cm^{-1} is also observed due to the bending vibrations of SO_2 group. Two absorption bands appeared below 3000 cm^{-1} at 2950 cm^{-1} and 2850 cm^{-1} respectively and these are assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric C–H stretching vibrations. The product analysis also confirms that there is no further reaction between dimethyl sulfone and chromium(VI)¹². Thus oxidation of DMSO by chromium(VI) is contrary to biological oxidation and falls in the category of chemical oxidations.

Results

The concentration of chromium(VI) was varied from 1.0×10^{-3} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients at 45 °C. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k' , s^{-1}) were evaluated from the pseudo-first order plots (Fig. 1).

The concentration of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was varied from 2.0×10^{-2} to 0.2 mol dm^{-3} at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients at 45 °C. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k' , s^{-1}) were calculated and a plot of k' versus [DMSO] yielded a straight line passing through the origin ascribing first order with respect to the substrate.

Fig. 1. A plot of $k/[H^+]^2$ versus $[H^+]$ in the reaction of chromium(VI) and dimethyl sulfoxide : $[DMSO] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $I = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The effect of ionic strength was studied by employing lithium perchlorate at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients at 45 °C. The rate increases with increasing ionic strength.

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration was studied by employing perchloric acid from 0.5 to 2.0 mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients and at $I = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (ionic strength I was adjusted by employing lithium perchlorate) at 40, 45 and 50 °C respectively. The rate increases with increasing concentration of hydrogen ion.

The effect of solvent on the rate of the reaction was studied by employing *n*-hexane from 5 to 40% in water-hexane (v/v) at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients. The rate of the reaction increases with increasing percentage of the solvent.

The effect of chloride ion on the rate was studied by employing sodium chloride at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients at 45 °C. The rate decreases with increasing concentration of chloride ion.

The effect of sodium nitrate and sodium acetate respectively was studied at fixed concentrations of reaction ingredients.

The rate decreases with decreasing concentrations of either of the salts. The enhancement in the rate on addition of sodium acetate may be attributed to the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium due to acetic acid. It appears that the hydroxyl hydrogen atom of chromium(VI) is replaced by acetyl group yielding a stronger electrophile

being more reactive than Cr^{VI}. Waters explained it by considering acetyl chromic acid AcCrO₂H or its conjugate base AcCrO₂OH₂⁺ to be the reactive form of the chromic acid. AcCrO₃⁻ has also been suggested to be the reactive form elsewhere.

Discussion

It has been emphasized in the reactions of chromium(VI) that the recognition of the effective oxidant species is necessary so that quantitative details about the equilibria governing such species are specified HCrO₄⁻ rather than Cr₂O₇²⁻ has now been accepted as the more common component of the transition state or activated complex in such reactions. The most probable and relevant equilibria involving chromium(VI) species are reported as follows :

There appears to be no connection between rate and [CrO₄²⁻] or rate and [Cr₂O₇²⁻] as has been revealed from the experimental observations. Thus the following equilibrium (5) is relevant so far the species of chromium(VI) are concerned under conditions of hydrogen ion concentration employed in the reactions.

It, therefore, confirms the fact that the reactive species is either HCrO₄⁻ or the chromium(VI) species of which concentration is directly proportional to [HCrO₄⁻].

The role of hydrogen ion is important in reactions of chromium(VI). However, it is worth mentioning that the order with respect to hydrogen ion in oxidations of sulfoxides reportedly^{32,33} varies from two to four. H₂CrO₄ or H₃CrO₄⁺ species of chromium(VI) to be the reactive species are assumed in oxidation of these sulfoxides. Since the reactions are second order viz. first order with respect to each reactant, the order with respect to hydrogen ion in the title reaction is in agreement with the empirical rate law (6).

$$\text{Rate} = \{Af_1[H^+] + Bf_2[H^+]\}[Cr^{VI}][DMSO] \quad (6)$$

where A and B are empirical constants.

It appears that the reaction proceeds by two paths,

one with two protons and other with three protons in addition to HCrO_4^- in the transition states (7) and (8).

Such a proposition is supported by the effect of solvent on the rate of the reaction as a plot of $\log k$ versus $1/[D]$ yields a straight line (here k is first order rate constant and ' D ' is dielectric constant of the solvent). Since solvent composition has been increased, its dielectric constant will decrease according to Scatchard's eq. (9).

$$\log k = e^2/2.3DkTr \quad (9)$$

where other terms have their usual meaning.

Turning to hydrogen ion dependence in rate eq. (6), $f_1[\text{H}^+]$ and $f_2[\text{H}^+]$ are the functions of hydrogen ion concentration. Various functions of hydrogen ion were tried but a plot of $k/[\text{H}^+]^2$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ is a straight line with positive intercept (Fig. 1). This leads to the fact that $f_1[\text{H}^+]$ is $[\text{H}^+]^2$ and $f_2[\text{H}^+]$ is $[\text{H}^+]^3$. Thus the rate eq. on substituting $f_1[\text{H}^+]$ and $f_2[\text{H}^+]$ terms in eq. (6) changes to eq. (10).

$$\text{Rate} = \{A[\text{H}^+]^2 + B[\text{H}^+]^3\}[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}][\text{DMSO}] \quad (10)$$

In view of such a rate law, the following reaction mechanism consisting of Paths 1 and 2 can be envisaged :

Path-1

Path-2

If these Paths 1 and 2 are taken into account; the rate law (19) is obtained.

$$-\frac{2}{3} \frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = \{k'_1 K'_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 + k'_2 K'_2 [\text{H}^+]^3\} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] [\text{DMSO}] \quad (19)$$

where $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ and $[\text{DMSO}]$ are the gross analytical concentrations of chromium(vi) and dimethyl sulfoxide respectively.

The formation of an adduct in step (12) of Path-1 and step (17) of Path-2 is indirectly supported by the effect of chloride ion as the rate decreases with increasing chloride ion. Such a decrease in rate with chloride ion can be accounted for blocking of coordination sites of chromium(vi) inhibiting incorporation of DMSO is the coordination shell of the oxidant.

The rate law (19) is further reduced to eq. (20).

$$k = k_1 K'_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 + k_2 K'_2 [\text{H}^+]^3 \quad (20)$$

where k is observed second order rate constant (Table 1).

Since K'_1 and K'_2 are small equilibrium constants, eq. (20) is reduced to (21).

$$k = k_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 + k_2 [\text{H}^+]^3 \quad (21)$$

where $k_1 = k_1 K'_1$ and $k_2 = k_2 K'_2$

k_1 was (calculated from the intercept) found to be 7.0×10^{-4} , 1.9×10^{-3} and $3.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and k_2 (from the slope) to be 5.8×10^{-3} , 7.2×10^{-3} and $8.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 40, 45 and 50 °C respectively at $I = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. These values of the rate constants k_1 and k_2 are comparable and thus both the paths are significant in the oxidation of dimethyl sulfoxide.

The energy and entropy of activation for path k_1 were calculated to be $(180 \pm 10) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(-275 \pm 20) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Similarly these were calculated for path (k_2) to be $(29 \pm 2) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(-196 \pm 20) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively.

The oxidation by chromate usually falls into two categories i.e. the reduction by one electron transfer or by two electron transfer processes as follows :

If this is the situation, a radical cation of DMSO.

Table 1. First order and second order rate constants in the reaction of chromium(vi) and dimethyl sulfoxide in aqueous acid solution
 $\text{HClO}_4 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 45 °C

$10^3 [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3 [\text{HCrO}_4^-]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2 [\text{DMSO}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^4 (k')$ (s^{-1})	$\frac{10^3(k)^a \times [\text{HCrO}_4^-]}{[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]} = k$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol s}^{-1}$)
2.0	1.8	2.5	1.63	5.85
2.0	1.8	3.0	1.79	5.31
2.0	1.8	3.5	2.04	5.22
2.0	1.8	4.0	2.30	5.13
2.0	1.8	4.5	2.68	5.31
2.0	1.8	5.0	2.87	5.13
2.0	1.8	6.0	3.83	5.67
2.0	1.8	7.0	4.22	5.40
2.0	1.8	8.0	4.60	5.13
2.0	1.8	10.0	6.14	5.49
3.0	4.1	3.0	1.24	5.60
3.0	4.1	3.5	1.66	6.40
3.0	4.1	4.0	1.73	5.87
3.0	4.1	4.5	1.82	5.46
3.0	4.1	5.0	1.91	5.19
3.0	4.1	6.0	2.68	6.00
3.0	4.1	7.0	2.87	5.60
3.0	4.1	8.0	3.45	5.87
3.0	4.1	10.0	4.22	5.74

^a HCrO_4^- species concentration was derived from the following relationship.

$$[\text{HCrO}_4^-] = [1 + 8K_d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] - 1]/4K_d$$

would have been formed with the formation of Cr^V species. Since acrylic acid on addition into the reaction mixture did not indicate polymerization, the possibility of any radical formation was ruled out. This exclusively, however, can not be considered as an evidence of formation of free radicals. There is every possibility that such a DMSO radical if formed, will hardly find time to escape out of the solvent cage in the presence of highly reactive and potential oxidant Cr^V. Thus the ultimate fate of the initial reaction events will result in the formation of Cr^{IV} or Cr^V without having any evidence of participation of either of them.

Inhibition by chloride ion :

There are various types of anions including chloride ion which are known to form complex with chromium(VI). Such a chloro-chromium(VI) species is less reactive than Cr^{VI}. Chloride ion forms a species like CrO₃Cl⁻ that reduces the concentration of reactive Cr^{VI} species as represented by eq. (22).

where Cr^{VI} is the concentration of chromium(VI) species that does not take into account the concentration of [CrO₃Cl⁻]. Moreover, such a chloride ion effect indirectly supports an adduct formation between Cr^{VI} and DMSO as an inhibition by Cl⁻ blocks the coordination sites of chromium(VI) for facile incorporation of the substrate in to coordination shell of the metal ion.

Eq. (23) is obtained from eq. (22),

$$K_{\text{Cl}^-} = \frac{[\text{CrO}_3\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}][\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (23)$$

If the inhibition by Cl⁻ is taken into account, an empirical form of the rate equation at constant hydrogen ion concentration can be given by eq. (24).

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_{\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}}[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}][\text{DMSO}] + k_{\text{Cl}^-}[\text{CrO}_3\text{Cl}^-][\text{DMSO}]}{1 + \frac{k_{\text{Cl}^-}}{k_{\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}}} \frac{[\text{CrO}_3\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}} \quad (24)$$

where k_{Cr} and k_{Cl^-} , respectively are the rate constants in absence and presence of chloride ion.

$$\text{Since } [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] + [\text{CrO}_3\text{Cl}^-] \quad (25)$$

Substituting [Cr^{VI}] and [CrO₃Cl⁻] from eqs. (23) and (24)

into eq. (25), and then re-arranging, eq. (26) is obtained.

$$K_{\text{Cl}^-} = k_{\text{Cr}} + \frac{1}{K_{\text{Cl}^-}} \left(\frac{k_{\text{Cr}} - k_{\text{Cl}^-}}{[\text{Cl}^-]} \right) \quad (26)$$

where, k_{Cl^-} is chloride ion inhibited observed rate constant.

Fig. 2. Plot of k_{Cl^-} versus $(k_{\text{Cr}} - k_{\text{Cl}^-})/[\text{Cl}^-]$ in the reaction of chromium(VI) and dimethyl sulfoxide.

A plot of k_{Cl^-} versus $\left(\frac{k_{\text{Cr}} - k_{\text{Cl}^-}}{[\text{Cl}^-]} \right)$ was made from eq. (26) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 2). k_{Cl^-} was calculated from the gradient to be $(18 \pm 2.0) \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 45 °C in fair agreement with the earlier reported²⁶ value of $17 \pm 2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 25 °C.

References

1. A. Chellamani and V. Rajarajeswari, *Afinidad*, 1999, **56**, 322.
2. C. Karunakaran and S. Suresh, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2000, **114**.
3. J. F. Perez-Benito, C. Arias, R. M. Rodriguez and M. Ros, *New J. Chem.*, 1998, **22**, 1445.
4. M. S. Elovitz and W. Fish, *Environ. Science and Technol.*, 1995, **29**, 1933.
5. S. R. Signorella, M. L. Santoro, M. N. Mulero and L. F. Sala, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1994, **72**, 398.
6. M. Abid and Z. Khan, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2003, **28**, 79.
7. S. A. Chimatadar, T. Basavaraj and S. T. Nandibewoor, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2003, **26**, 88.

8. Kabir-ud-din, A. M. A. Morshed and Z. Khan, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2003, **35**, 543.
9. L. Legrand, A. El-Figuigui, F. Mercier and A. Chausse, *Environ. Science and Technol.*, 2004, **38**, 4587.
10. A. Levina and P. A. Lay, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2005, **249**, 281.
11. S. Garcia, L. Ciullo, M. S. Olivera, J. C. Gonzalez, S. Bellu, A. Rockenbauer, L. Korecz and L. F. Sala, *Polyhedron*, 2006, **25**, 1483.
12. D. Park, Y.-S. Yun, C. K. Ahn and J. M. Park, *Chemosphere*, 2007, **66**, 939.
13. M. Santoro, E. Caffaratti, J. M. Salas-Pelegrin, L. Korecz, A. Rockenbauer, L. F. Sala and S. Signorella, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 169.
14. S. Meenakshisundaram and N. Sarathi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2007, **46**, 1778.
15. P. N. Naik, S. A. Chimatadar and S. T. Nandibewoor, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2008, **33**, 405.
16. J. C. Gonzalez, S. Garcia, S. Bellu, A. Sebastian, A. M. Atria, J. M. Salas-Pelegrin, A. Rockenbauer, L. Korecz, S. Signorella and L. F. Sala, *Polyhedron*, 2009, **28**, 2719.
17. F. H. Westheimer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1949, **45**, 419.
18. W. A. Waters, in "Mechanism of Oxidation of Organic Compounds", Methuen & Co. Ltd., London, 1964.
19. R. Stewart, in "Oxidation Mechanism", Benjamin, Inc., New York, 1964.
20. K. B. Wiberg, in "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", Academic Press Inc., New York, 1964.
21. J. Rocek, in "Chemistry of Carbonyl Group", ed. S. Patai, Interscience Publishers, Inc., London, 1966.
22. F. Freeman, in "Reviews on Reactive Species in Chemical Reactions", ed. Dayagi, Freund Publishing House, Tel Aviv, Israel, 1973, 36.
23. J. K. Beattie and G. P. Haight (Jr.), *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **17**, 93.
24. S. Sundaram, N. Venkatasubramanian and S. V. Ananta Krishnan, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1976, **35**, 518.
25. G. V. Bakore and C. L. Jain, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 805.
26. D. A. Durham, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3549.
27. H. Fariza and J. Rocek, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 534 and references cited therein.
28. A. G. Davies, "Organic Peroxides", Butterworths and Co. Ltd., London, 1961; S. R. Reddy, J. S. Reddy, R. Kumar and P. Kumar, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 84; M. Sklorz and J. Binert, *Envir. Sci. and Pollut. Res.*, 1994, **1**, 140; S. H. Zinder and T. D. Brock, *Arch. Microbiol.*, 1978, **116**, 35.
29. C. Srinivasan, R. Venkatasami and S. Rajagopal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **20**, 505.
30. V. Baliah and P. V. V. Satyanarayan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 619.
31. L. I. Simandi, M. Jaky and A. M. Khenkin, *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, 1987, **134**, 187.
32. D. Bhatta, S. M. Behera and S. R. Mohanty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 778.
33. S. Venkateswara Rao and V. Jagannadham, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 252.
34. C. Srinivasan and P. P. Jegatheesan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 250.

